

Impact of Climate Change on Paddy Yield; An empirical study Based on Hambantota District

B.K.H.D. Anuranga
Department of Commerce and Financial Management
University of Kelaniya
Sri Lanka
bkhdanuranga123@gmail.com
T: P 0713992164

Abstract

The intergovernmental panel on climate change (IPCC) defines Climate Change (CC) as the change in the state of the climate that can be identified (using statistical tests) by the changes in the mean and or the variability of its properties and, that persists for an extended period, typically decade or longer". Paddy cultivation is highly vulnerable to CC and subsequently its yield determines how much income is earned by farmers. This study was undertaken by the researcher to ascertain whether there is a relationship between CC on paddy yield gained by farmers in Hambantota district as the same study dedicated to Hambantota District has had not been done. Data, temperature and rainfall, for a period of 30 years otherwise mentioned as the sample size of sixty samples representing both in Yala and Maha were obtained from the Meteorological Department in Sri Lanka at the same time paddy yield in Hambantota district was also used and regression analysis used in quantitative method analysis was employed in determining whether CC has an impact on paddy yield gained the. The researcher built following hypotheses for the model, Rise in temperature may impact on crop yield to fall down, fall in temperature may impact on Crop yield to fall down, and Rise may impact Crop Yield to increase. It was found out that temperature has a significant impact on paddy yield whereas rainfall has no significant impact on paddy yield. Additionally, an independent predictor variable, extent of land made a significant impact on paddy yield. To mitigate the adverse effects of CC, enlarging the extent of land cultivated and remedial actions to be taken to control the adverse impact by rise in temperature were also suggested.

Key Words: **Climate Change, Extent of land cultivated, Paddy yield.**

1. Introduction

The intergovernmental panel on climate change (IPCC)¹ defines Climate Change (CC) as the change in the state of the climate that can be identified (using statistical tests) by the changes in the mean and or the variability of its properties and, that persists for an extended period, typically decade or longer". The definition refers to any change in climate over time either due to natural variability or human activities. This is different from the definition of the United Nations framework convention on climate change (UNFCCC), where CC is defined to be a change of climate that is attributed directly or indirectly to human activities that alters the composition of global atmosphere and that is addition to natural climate variability observed over comparable time period. After the fourth assessment report (IPCC, 2007) , which projected an alarming increase in global average temperature in the range 0.3-6.4 0 C at the end of the twenty first century. The experts' reports say further that the greenhouse gases GHG, which are the major causes of Atmospheric carbon dioxide concentration (CO₂) and the in 2008 (387 parts per million(ppm)) was the highest on record in human history (NOAA, 2009). There is hardly any skepticism that climate is changing; carbon dioxide (CO₂) concentrations in the atmosphere are rising, as are temperatures (Lenny Bernstein, 2007). According to meteorological department in Sri Lanka, during 1961 and 1990 the country's mean air temperature increased by 0.016 and mean annual precipitation decreased by 144 millimeters 7% compared to that of 1931 and 1960 (Basnayake, 2011). However, it is important to have known what and how future climate might behave for, this has its implications to paddy cultivation subsequently to its yield and the paddy yield gained by farmers determines how much income is earned by farmers thus results in prevention of feeling of deprivation and otherwise known as human needs. There will be changes in the mean and variance of rainfall and temperature, extreme weather events, food and agriculture production and prices, water availability and access, nutrition and health status. The most significant features are in developing country like Sri Lanka, rather a poor district, Hambantota, compared to other districts having climate sensitive sectors, low incomes, and weak adaptive capacity, Socio-economic impacts. Although generally not well understood, impacts associated with paddy cultivation are likely to be profound and will impact humans through a variety of direct and indirect pathways (IPCC, Contribution of Working Group II to the Fourth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, 2007). From the total poverty percentage, 84.7% is represented by the rural sector accentuating a significant amount compared to both urban and estate sector which report poverty percentage 8.8%, 6.5% respectively (Department of Census and Statistics, 2007). Hence, it is evident that people living in rural areas, including Hambantota, are poor, this research focused on finding out weather the so called climate change has influenced the crop yield gained and subsequently the income earned by farmers. Another objective of this research was to check whether there is a relationship between climatic change and climatic impact on crop yield and farmers' income and rural poverty. In the early part of the year 2011 country experienced a detrimental aberration in precipitation causing damages to crop yield especially paddy cultivation. Consequently, the damaged crop yield reported was 26% of the total paddy yield that would have been harvested otherwise and this damage caused farmers to lose their crop yield and consequently lost in income by the same percentage (Department of Census and statistics, 2012). Therefore, climatic implication on poverty is an important area and this has not been

¹ The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) is the leading international body for the assessment of climate change. It was established by the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) in 1988.

taken into consideration by the authorities in Sri Lanka and the department of census and statistics itself has not collected information or data on climate impact on farmer's income and poverty in Hambantota district. As discussed above, poverty may be caused by several reasons and one of which has received little attention is the poverty that takes place due to climate change.

1.2 Objectives of the Study

- 1 This study attempts to find out whether the so called changes in climate have implications on paddy yield in Hambantota district.
- 2 To check the accuracy of the claim rise in temperature has an impact on paddy yield in Hambantota District.

2. Literature Review

This chapter discusses the stances and other researches done on the topic of the impact of climatic changes on paddy harvesting and is expected to pave the way for a new area to be considered important. Most importantly, the rural poverty rate in Sri Lanka is reported nearly 85% out of the total poverty rate 7.6%. There are many chronic reasons as to why rural people remain impoverished. This attempt is to reveal the experts' views on poverty and climate change. Rural poverty occurs with livelihood associated with agriculture; Agriculture is highly vulnerable to climate change and therefore changes in the atmospheric condition thus results in climate variations determining the crop yield and subsequently the income earned by farmers. In terms of climate changes in Sri Lanka, it can also be observed undergoing some changes in the climate condition and key noticeable features among them are the expansion of the dry land extent in the country. This expansion in the dry land extent has been studied and proved by a research done (Nishadi Eriyagama, 2010). It has been examined the impact of temperature rises on agricultural yields, output, income and prices. With a temperature increase of 2 °C and an accompanying precipitation increase of 7%, farm level total net revenue is estimated to fall by 9%, whereas, with a temperature increase of 3.5 °C and precipitation increase of 15%, the fall in farm level total net revenue would be nearly 25%. Beyond the direct economic impacts, crop failure due to climate change could also increase unemployment, destabilized food security, further increase competition for scarce resources, and increase social inequity (Rahman, 2007). Further, the reports stated that "*Climate change is a serious risk to poverty reduction and threatens to undo decades of development efforts*" (Sperling, 2003). Research organizations such as the Climate Change Knowledge Network, The Energy and Resources Institute (TERI), the Stockholm Environment Institute (SEI), the Institute of Development Studies (IDS) and the International Institute for Environment and Development (IIED) have all extended climate research to include development issues. For example, the livelihoods approach in development research has now been incorporated into climate studies to assess vulnerability (Burton I., 2002). This has improved links between income earned associated with crop cultivation and subsequently poverty and climate vulnerability. Despite these efforts, most government agencies in developing and least developed countries, and most local-level development groups, still do not adequately incorporate climate change into their development activities (U.S. Agency for International Development, 2012). The southwest monsoon (SWM) is from May to September and northeastern monsoon (NEM) from December to February by which districts like Hambantota and dry Zones receive most of their precipitation for agricultural

purposes. There are two inter monsoonal from March to April (first inter monsoon (IM1)) and from October to November (second inter monsoon (IM2)) and the EL Nino-southern Oscillation (ENSO) is known to influence the country' rainfall (Suppaiah, 1996) . Sri Lanka mainly consists of three climatic zones: Wet Zone, Dry Zone, and Intermediate Zone Descriptive analysis of rainfall data reveals decline in total rainfall in the wet and intermediate zones and these changes in rainfall patterns seem to be being experienced by paddy farmers whose planting and harvesting patterns have changed over the past 20 years. Paddy is highly vulnerable to variation in temperature and rainfall (Panbokke, 1974) taking. Impacts of CC can be seen in three forms namely temperature, CO₂, and precipitation on crop growth. Higher temperatures are associated with higher radiation and higher water use. 0.1-0.5 ° C increase in temperature can reduce rice yield by approximately 1-5%. He also states that recent agro-meteorological observations have shown that frequency of such temperature increased significantly in the dry and intermediate zones, especially during Yala season and this has resulted in a high rate of unfilled grains due to increased spikelet sterility (Vidanage, 1994) . Recent evidence and predictions highlight that climate changes are accelerating and will lead to wide-ranging shifts in climate variables. The threat posed by the change in climate in Sri Lanka is at its crescendo given the projection made by experts saying that the mean temperature in Sri Lanka may increase by approximately 0.9-4 (over the base line) by 2100 with associated changes in the quantity and spatial distribution of rainfall. Further these changes may lead to an increase in Maha² season irrigation water requirement for paddy by 13 % to 23% by 2050 compared to that of 1961 – 1990 (N.Eriyagama, 2010). The spatial pattern of the precipitation is strongly influenced by topography and there are two seasonal wind regimes (Chandrapala, 1996).

3. Methods

Shown below is the Conceptual frame work for the study undertaken by the researcher and this model has been backed by the researchers in literatures in the literature review.

3.1 Conceptual Frame work

Figure: 01 Conceptual Framework

² One of the two agricultural seasons in Sri Lanka” Yala from April to September, Maha from October to March.

3.2 Data and Sampling

Firstly, it is estimated the responses of crop yields both in Yala and Maha, agricultural seasons, Independent variable to climate change. Climate change was referred to the changes in average temperature and precipitation, both are dependent variables obtained from the Department of Meteorology, prevailed for the period of thirty years starting from 1983 to 2012 thus thirty years of paddy cultivation illustrates sixty sample units given both seasonal effects Yala and Maha and data for extent of land cultivated was obtained from Hector Kobbekaduwa Agrarian, Research and Training Institute of Sri Lanka for Hambantota district for both the seasons for a period of thirty years.

3.3 Variables

3.3.1 Dependent Variable

Paddy yield in Hambantota were put as the dependent variable in this study for the period of thirty years, both Yala and Maha agricultural seasons due to which thirty years sample reflects sixty sample size to be taken starting from 1983 to 2012 and the data were obtained from Hector Kobbekaduwa Agrarian, Research and Training Institute (HARTI) in Sri Lanka.

3.3.2 Independent Variables

A. Temperature

Data pertaining to which were obtained from the Department of Meteorology in Sri Lanka for the same period and data were further classified in to Yala and Maha seasons' temperature figures in this study for thirty years reflecting sixty sample size.

B. Rainfall

Data pertaining to this study were obtained from the Department of Meteorology in Sri Lanka for the same period and data were further classified in to Yala and Maha Rainfall figures.

C. Extent of Land Cultivated

Data for this were obtained from the Hector Kobbekaduwa Agrarian, Research and Training Institute (HARTI) in Sri Lanka for the period of thirty years otherwise reflecting sixty sample size starting from 1983 to 2012 with effect for both Yala and Maha seasons.

The multiple regression model for the study has been employed to assess the significant determinants of paddy yield in Hambantota district. To measure the significant determinants, temperature, rainfall and extent of land cultivated have been taken as independent variable while paddy yield has been taken as the Dependent variable. The regression model for the above model is shown as follows.

3.4 Model of the Study

Model was developed based on regression analysis by the researcher to ascertain the mentioned scenario and it is as follows.

$$Y = \beta_1 + \beta_2 X_1 + \beta_3 X_2 + \beta_4 X_3 + e$$

Where, Y= Crop yield, β_1 = Intercept Beta, β_2 = Beta coefficient of temperature, X_1 = Temperature (Average), β_3 = Beta coefficient of precipitation, X_2 = Rain fall (Average), β_4 =Beta coefficient of extent of land cultivated, X_3 = Extent of land, e = Random error term.

3.5 Hypotheses developed in the Model

There are several hypothesis developed for the study is shown as follows.

Table 01

Hypothesis	Dependent variable	Independent variables	Hypotheses
H ₁	Paddy Yield	Temperature	Rise in temperature may impact on crop yield to fall down
H ₂		Rain fall	Fall in temperature may impact on Crop yield to fall down
H ₃		Extent of land cultivated	Rise may impact Crop Yield to increase

4. Analysis and Discussions

4.1 Regression Analysis

The purpose of the regression analysis is to find out the significant impact or influence of independent variables on the dependent variable (Hair, 2011).

Table 02: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.538 ^a	.289	.251	442.57589	1.322
a. Predictors: (Constant), Extent of Land, Rainfall, Temperature					
b. Dependent Variable: Crop Yield					

As per the table 02 a moderate level of model fit was observed by R (54%) value of the study. R square value of 29% does not imply a significant explanatory power of the model. Say it simply, variables of extent of land, rainfall and temperature do not explain the dependent variable of crop yield heavily. Further, table 03 affirms the overall model fit of the study suggesting a significant P value of 0.000 significant under significance level of 10%. Thus it can be postulated that the overall model is fitted with the variables identified.

Table 03: ANOVA table in the regression analysis

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	4462670.938	3	1487556.979	7.594	.000 ^b
	Residual	10968911.518	56	195873.420		
	Total	15431582.455	59			
a. Dependent Variable: Crop Yield						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Extent of Land, Rainfall, Temperature						

Above ANOVA regressions and residuals table depict that over all model fit is significant at 5% level of significance. Which means the p value of .000 is significant under the desired level of significance. The variables of crop yield, extent of land, rainfall and temperature hold a very significant relationship among the variables.

Table 04: Coefficients table for the regression analysis

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	8835.787	1862.724		4.743	.000
	Temperature	-188.853	65.216	-.366	-2.896	.005
	Rainfall	2.490	1.812	.171	1.374	.175
	Extent of Land	.028	.015	.252	1.944	.057

a. Dependent Variable: Crop Yield

As per the table 04, increase in temperature by 1 C ° may result decrease in paddy yield by approximately 189 Kg and this relationship is statistically significant. Also rise in extent of land by 1 hectare may increase paddy yield by 0.28 Kg. However, Rise or fall in temperature is not significant and change in rainfall per 1mm may change the paddy yield by approximately by 2.5 Kg per hectare which not so much significant to be taken to consideration. Finally, it can be state that rise in extent of land has a significant (10% significant level) impact on crop yield suggesting .028 change for crop yield. These relationships imply that the annotations of the variables of temperature and extent of land imply causality for crop yield. Thus the researcher states that temperature and extend of land are significant predictor variables of crop yield.

4.2 Hypotheses Testing

Summary of data analysis is given below through hypothesis testing

Table: 05 Hypotheses Results

No	Hypotheses	Result	Tools
H ₁	Rise in temperature decreases paddy yield	Accepted	Regression
H ₂	Fall in rainfall decreases paddy yield	Rejected	Regression
H ₃	Rise in extent of land cultivated increases paddy yield	Accepted	Regression

As per the results appeared in the table 04, co-efficient table, It clearly demonstrates that the changes in the climate, considered for the period of 30 years, both changes in temperature and rainfall, only the temperature has made a significant influence on paddy yield and thus the hypothesis H₁ is accepted whereas the Hypothesis H₂ is rejected as it has no significant impact in determining the paddy yield. Additionally, the extent of land cultivated is found to have a significant impact on paddy yield gained therefore the Hypothesis H₃ is accepted.

5. Conclusion

In the attempt to find out whether the so called climate change has impact on paddy yield gained in Hambantota district and specifically rise in temperature impacts on paddy cultivation, it was empirically found out by means of employing Regression analysis, statistical model, that rainfall makes no significant impact on paddy yield, this could also be attributable to the watering for paddy is done through irrigation thus providing water supply adequately and consistently to paddy fields, and finally, it can be stated that both rise in temperature and rise in extent of land cultivated have a significant (10% significant level) impact on crop yield. These relationships imply that the annotations of the variables, temperature and extent of land imply causality for crop yield thus filling the research gap identified the researcher concludes that temperature and extend of land are statistically significant predictor variables of crop yield, Moreover, rise in temperature brings down crop yield and rise in extent of land cultivated brings up the paddy yield. Thus alleviating poverty among poverty in Hambantota district, as many families livelihood is associated with paddy cultivation, it is noteworthy if the measurements are being made on attending to the significant predictor variables, extent of land cultivated and temperature. Accordingly, it can be suggested to employing bare lands for cultivation in Hambantota district and proper measurements to be taken to control the implication of rise in temperature.

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